

Influence of Lyophilized Rumen Fluid Challenge on Egyptian Buffalo Calves affected with Simple Indigestion

Ahmed E. Mahmoud^{1*}, Essam S. Soliman², Fawzy M. Abo-Donia³ and Tharwat S. Nafie¹

¹Department of Veterinary Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt 41522

²Department of Animal Hygiene, Zoonosis & Animal Behavior, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt. 41522

³Animal Production Research Institute, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

Abstract

Fresh rumen fluid was collected from slaughtered house in Ismailia governorate and lyophilized; then administered for Egyptian buffalo calves suffered from simple indigestion. Ten buffalo calves were divided into 2 groups (Five calves for each group); the 1st group suffered from simple indigestion and were challenged with lyophilized rumen fluid (LRF) for 7 consecutive days, and a 2nd control group. Ruminal fluid samples were collected at zero time before challenge; and at 1, 2, and 3 weeks post challenge. The study revealed that buffalo calves suffered from simple indigestion showed a highly significant reduction in ruminal pH, protozoal motility, total protozoal; total bacterial; lactobacillus and ruminococcus counts in addition to ammonia, SCFA's and glucose level in ruminal fluid. Also, the study revealed a significant increase in the total bacterial; total protozoal counts, and count of lactobacillus and ruminococcus. Furthermore, there were a significant increase of ruminal lactate, ammonia and glucose level after treatment of indigestion with LRF compared with its level at zero time before challenge. Environmental temperature and relative humidity recording in order revealed strong positive; strong positive, strong negative; strong negative, strong positive; very strong positive, weak positive; strong negative, weak negative; positive, weak negative; weak positive, very strong positive; weak positive, weak negative; strong negative, and weak negative; weak positive correlations to ruminal pH; protozoal motility; log TPC; log TBC; log Lactobacillus count; log Ruminococcus count; levels of glucose; lactate; ammonia, respectively.

Key words: Lyophilized rumen fluid, indigestion, buffalo calves, bacterial & protozoal counts.

1. Introduction

Ruminant animals are great contributors to the human food chain due to their ability to utilize complex polysaccharides in plant cell walls (cellulose, hemicelluloses and pectin) and turn these into meat and milk for human consumption. Digestion of these polysaccharides in ruminant is attributable to anaerobic biodegradation of these compounds into their respective monomers by microorganisms present in the forestomach of the animals; **William, et al., (2014)**. Rumen is considered the most important organ in ruminants as it performs the most important digestive function, it is a

natural anaerobic ecosystem in which microbial digestion of feedstuffs occurs; **Nagaraja and Titgemeyer, (2007)**. Collection of ruminal fluid is important in disease diagnosis, therapy, and scientific research in ruminants; **Shen, et al., (2012)** as it contains a mixed community of microorganisms consisting of bacteria (10^{10} - 10^{11} cells/ml), ciliate protozoa (10^4 - 10^6 /ml) and anaerobic fungi (10^3 - 10^5 zoospores/ml); **Kamra (2005); Houda Bouraoui, et al., (2011); Nikki Kenters, et al., (2011)**. These different microbes form a mixed complex community that interact with each other play

a very important role in fermentation of food stuff to produce useful end products needed for animal growth in the form of volatile fatty acids which are absorbed across the rumen wall and used as a key energy source for animal and ammonia which is used as a nitrogen source for microbial growth; **Deng, et al., (2008)**; **Adrian, et al., (2004)**. Rumen disorders had a greater clinical interest because of the high morbidity and the great losses in both production and cost of treatment of the affected ruminants furthermore the great losses caused by ruminal diseases, so examination of the ruminal juice is usually used as an indicator for its function, **Ratib, (2001)**. The fluctuation in temperature and humidity exerts effects on animal physiology and performance as well as the ruminal bacterial diversity; which altered significantly in response to raised temperature; **Tajima, et al., (2007)**. Although temperature has significant effects on ruminal fermentation patterns and gas production; **Bhatta, et al., (2006)**. In Egypt, the ruminal contents produced from slaughter of animals in abattoirs were not used and get rid of it to constitute a great source of environmental pollution, so the major objectives of this study is to investigate the influence of lyophilized ruminal fluid challenge on treatment of simple indigestion in ruminants and to find a suitable beneficial method for hygienic disposal, preservation and recycling of these important materials to be reused for treatment of indigestion in ruminants in addition to overcome the risk of drenching pneumonia by lyophilization of rumen fluid to overcome the problems of handling of fresh rumen fluid.

2. Material and methods

The present experiment was conducted at educational animal farm, Collage of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt.

2.1. Rumen inoculum preparation

Rumen fluid was collected from Ismailia governorate abattoir, Egypt into thermos insulated drink container, pre-warmed 39°C, flushed with CO₂ and sealed before being transported to the laboratory then strained

through four layer of cheesecloth and maintained at 39°C before being freeze drying; **Abo-Donia, et al., (2011)**. Ruminal fluid was freeze-dried using a vacuum freeze dryer (Lab Conoco. USA) in animal reproduction research institute, Giza, Egypt. Dry matter yield of the rumen fluid was 3.9% (each 100ml fresh rumen fluid (FRF) yield 3.9gm freeze-dried rumen fluid). Lyophilized rumen fluid (LRF) was prepared by using 3.9gm freeze-dried rumen fluid diluted with 100 ml isotonic saline and inoculated for each calf.

2.2. Animals and treatments

A total number of ten male Egyptian buffalo calves of 5 months old age with average live weight of 110kg were selected and assigned into two groups, 5 calves for each; the first group (G1) suffered from simple indigestion which diagnosed based on the clinical examination of animals; **Radostits, et al., (2007)**, and the second group (G2) act as a control healthy group. Calves of the 1st group (G1) were challenged with 12gm LRF; that was drenched directly for 7 successive days; **Zhong, et al., (2014)** during which the environmental temperature and relative humidity were recorded on daily basis as well as during sample collection days using Clock & Hygro-Thermometer, (Boeco Germany, model: BOE 325); Indoor/Outdoor-MIN/MAX Thermometer, (Boeco Germany, model: BOE 325). Buffalo calves during the period of study were kept together under open half shelter system and fed on a mixture of a concentrate diet and roughage, the concentrate consisted of 30% ground yellow corn, 15% DDGS (Distiller's dried grains with soluble), 26.5% wheat bran, 10% dried beet pulp, 15% sunflower seed meal, 1.5% ground lime stone, 0.6% mineral premix, 0.5% vitamin premix and 0.9% sodium chloride. Wheat straw was used as roughage at a rate of 2kg per calf, buffalo calves were fed concentrate diet at a rate of 2.5 - 3kg per day per calf divided into three feeding times daily and tap water was provided ad libitum.

2.3. Sampling and measurements

2.3.1. Samples: A total number of 40 ruminal fluid samples were obtained from

all animals (four samples per each calf) during the experiment at zero time before inoculation, 1 week, 2 week and 3 week from starting LRF challenge. Samples were transferred in thermos insulated drink container, pre-warmed 39°C and flushed with CO₂ within half hour from collection to the research laboratory at department of Internal Animal Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Egypt. Ruminal fluid samples (250ml) were collected from each calf using stomach tube with a conical flask connected to its free end, while a vacuum pump was connected to the side tube of the flask; **Shen, et al., (2012); Lodge-Ivey, et al., (2009).**

2.3.2. Ruminal fluid analysis: each sample was divided into three portions. The first one (50ml) was used for estimation of ruminal fluid pH and evaluation of protozoal activity, rumen fluid pH was measured immediately after collection of samples using a calibrated electronic digital portable pH meter (Hanna instruments, Italy); **Abo-Donia, et al., (2011); Bramley, et al., (2008); Hajikolaie, et al., (2006).** To Judge the activity and population density of the protozoa, one drop of rumen fluid was placed on a gently warmed glass slide and then covered with a cover slip and examined under 4 x lens magnification, it was described as highly motile and abundant (+ + +), motile and moderate number (+ +), sluggish and low number (+), no or sporadic alive protozoa (±) and dead protozoa (-); **Fouda, (1995).** The second part (100ml) was strained through 4 layers of cheesecloth then centrifuged for 15 minutes at 4000rpm, clear supernatant fluid was poured off into a clean plastic tube and was kept frozen at -20°C until used for the biochemical analysis of lactate, ammonia and glucose levels that were estimated calorimetrically using reagent test kits supplied by Ben company, Italy; **Young, (2001),** Bio-diagnostic company, Egypt; **Konitzer and Voigt, (1963)** and Diamond company, Egypt; **Young, (2001),** respectively. Spectrophotometric assay was performed using photometer 5010 in department of

Animal Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, Ismailia, Egypt. About 2ml aliquot of collected ruminal fluid was placed into a glass bottle contain 1ml of sulfuric acid (0.1M) and kept frozen at -20°C for subsequent analysis of short chain fatty acids (SCFA's) by gas chromatography; **Abo-Donia, et al., (2011)** in Animal Production Research Institute (APRI), Dokki, Giza, Egypt. The remaining part (100ml) was kept to conduct the microscopical count of ruminal protozoa and microbiological culture of rumen bacteria.

2.3.3. Rumen protozoal count in rumen content:

A well strained 1.0ml of ruminal fluid was diluted 5 times with saline lugol's iodine mixture solution (15ml saline solution and 5ml lugol's solution) to fix and stain the protozoal cells. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and exactly 0.1ml was poured on a dry clean slide and spread under a cover slip of 1100mm² area (22 x 50mm). Care was taken when fitting the cover slip to avoid any air bubbles or escape of some fluid out of the area. Counting was carried out using a low power lens. Thirty fields were counted in each slide. The field area of the lens was 1mm², and the average protozoal counts in 30 fields represents 0.2ml of the original sample, therefore, to get the protozoal count per ml of ruminal contents, the obtained value was multiplied by 50, thus the total protozoal count (TPC)/ml of ruminal fluid was calculated according to the following equation: **Salah Abd-Elmohsen Galbt, (2007); Wang, et al., (2009).** $TPC = (\text{Total protozoal counts in 30 fields} / 30) \times 1100 \times 50$

2.3.4. Bacteriological examination of ruminal fluid:

2.3.4.1. Preparation of samples:

All ruminal fluid samples were prepared according to the technique recommended by **APHA, (2001).** Ruminal fluid samples were kept in incubator after collection. From the original sample, 1ml was transferred aseptically to a test tube containing 9ml sterile anaerobic dilution solution (ADS) to prepare a dilution of 10⁻¹, from which tenfold decimal serial dilution up to 10⁻⁸

were prepared to cover the expected range of colonial growth. The tubes were flushed with carbon dioxide to enhance the anaerobic conditions; **Chandrasekharaiah, et al., (2004)**.

The composition of ADS was as follows: (I) Mineral solution I- 0.3% dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, 15.0ml; (II) Mineral solution II- 0.3% potassium hydrogen phosphate + 0.6% ammonium sulfate + 0.6% sodium chloride + 0.6% magnesium sulfate + 0.06% calcium chloride, 15.0 ml; cysteine hydrochloride, 0.05%; sodium carbonate, 0.3%; resazurin, 0.001%; and distilled water, to make up to 100ml. The ADS was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C and 1.5 pressure for 20 minute, after cooling; the diluent was displaced into tubes; each tube containing 9ml to be ready for serial dilution; **Chandrasekharaiah, et al., (2004)**.

2.3.4.2. Total Anaerobic Bacterial Count (TABC): Total number of anaerobic microorganisms in ruminal fluid samples was counted by Pour Plate Method; **Cruickshank et al., (1975-1980)** using Standard Plate Count Agar (SPCA). One ml from each dilution as well as the original samples were aseptically transferred into sterile Petri-dishes, starting with the highest dilution, after which 10 ml of Standard Plate Count Agar, previously melted and cooled at 45°C as well as treated with anti-fungal growth agents (Cyclo-heximide 0.5ml /100ml agar + Amphotricin-B 1.5ml/100ml agar) were added and mixed thoroughly in a horizontal position; **Jens Christian Pedersen, (1992)**; **Mahdy, et al., (2010)**. After solidification, inoculated plates were inverted and placed in anaerobic jar using Carbon dioxide gas producing kits. The jar was placed in incubator at 37°C for 72 hours. Counting the colonies on the plates showed 30-300 colonies per plates. The calculation was carried out using the following formula: $\text{Log (average CFU/ drop vol.)} \times (\text{Dilution factor}) \times (\text{Vol. scrapped into/ surface area})$, **Herigstad, et al., (2001)**; **Zelver, et al., (1999)**.

2.3.4.3. Total Lactobacillus count

Total number of lactobacillus species in ruminal fluid samples was counted by Pour Plate Method; **Cruickshank et al., (1975-1980)** using lactobacillus selective medium (MRS) agar; **Anwar A Abdulla, (2014)**; **Patrick, et al., (1999)**. One ml from each dilution as well as the original samples were aseptically transferred into sterile Petri-dishes, starting with the highest dilution, after which 10 ml of MRS agar previously melted and cooled at 45°C, were added and mixed thoroughly in a horizontal position. After solidification, inoculated plates were inverted and placed in anaerobic jar using carbon dioxide gas producing kits. The jar was placed in incubator at 37°C for 72 hours. Counting the colonies showed white bacillary or rode appearance on the plate. The calculation was carried out using the following formula: $\text{Log (average CFU/ drop vol.)} \times (\text{Dilution factor}) \times (\text{Vol. scrapped into/ surface area})$; **Herigstad, et al., (2001)**; **Zelver, et al., (1999)**.

2.3.4.4. Total Ruminococcus count

Total number of Ruminococcus species as one of the cellulolytic bacteria in ruminal fluid was counted by Pour Plate Method; **Cruickshank et al., (1975-1980)** using Rumen Glucose Cellobiose Agar (RGCA) media after incubating the samples at 39°C for 72 hours of incubation; **Chandrasekharaiah, et al., (2004)**. RGCA Medium used for the isolation of the cellulolytic bacteria was as follows: clarified rumen fluid, 20.0%; glucose, 0.0248g; cellobiose, 0.0248g; ammonium sulfate, 0.1g; agar, 2.0g /100ml; mineral solutions I and II, 15% each; haemin, 50mg; vitamin K1, 0.1mg; L-cysteine hydrochloride, 0.5mg; resazurin, 0.1mg/100 ml; distilled water, to make up to 100ml; **Chandrasekharaiah, et al., (2004)**. One ml from each dilution as well as the original samples were aseptically transferred into sterile Petri-dishes, starting with the highest dilution, after which 10ml of RGCA, previously melted and cooled at 45°C, were added and mixed thoroughly in a horizontal position. After solidification, inoculated plates were inverted and placed in anaerobic

jar using carbon dioxide gas producing kits. The jar was placed in incubator at 37°C for 72 hours. Counting the colonies with zone of hydrolysis on the plates. The calculation was carried out using the following formula: $\text{Log (average CFU/ drop vol.)} \times (\text{Dilution factor}) \times (\text{Vol. scrapped into/ surface area})$; Herigstad, et al., (2001); Zelter, et al., (1999).

3. Statistical analysis:

The obtained data were analyzed statistically using factorial experiments of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with general linear model procedures (GLM) for all tested groups, times and their interactions; Snedecor and Cochran, (1989). For means separation, Duncan's Multiple Range test (DMRT) was used and the results are considered significant at probability level of 0.05 ($P \leq 0.05$); Duncan, (1955). Statistical analysis was run through SPSS (version, 20) for windows; Levesque, (2007). The mean values, standard error (SE) were calculated

by using Microsoft Excel program. For protozoal and bacterial count a logarithmic transformation were done before analysis. The correlation co-efficient was calculated to compare the influence of each measured parameter mean values on each other; Fulekar, (2009); Stigler, (1989).

3. Results & Discussion

The observed clinical signs were inappetance, loss of body weight and reduced frequency of ruminal activity, one cycle per 2 minute, and became weak in strength and incomplete (ruminal atony) with firm ruminal contents which give dull sound on percussion. These clinical signs were relieved at the 1st week of LRF challenge where the animals regain its normal previous appetite, ruminate again with normal ruminal motility (3 cycle per 2 minutes), moderate in strength & complete with resilient on palpation and tympanic sound on percussion.

Table 1. The mean values \pm S.E of ambient temperature and relative humidity in relation to time factors (administration of LRF for Egyptian buffalo calves and collection of ruminal fluid samples).

	Time	Ambient temperature	Relative humidity %
Period of LRF administration	Day 1	29 ^a \pm 0.94	54.7 ^h \pm 0.72
	Day 2	29 ^a \pm 0.47	49.7 ⁱ \pm 0.72
	Day 3	30.8 ^a \pm 0.59	82 ^c \pm 0.47
	Day 4	29.3 ^a \pm 0.72	91.3 ^b \pm 0.72
	Day 5	30.2 ^a \pm 0.49	73.7 ^d \pm 0.27
	Day 6	29.5 ^a \pm 0.71	75.3 ^d \pm 0.720
	Day 7	29.5 ^a \pm 0.71	64.3 ^f \pm 0.72
Time of samples	Zero	30.5 ^a \pm 0.62	62 ^g \pm 0.47
	1 st week	30.2 ^a \pm 0.36	65.3 ^f \pm 0.72
	2 nd week	29 ^a \pm 0.47	69 ^e \pm 0.47
	3 rd week	29.8 ^a \pm 0.95	97.7 ^a \pm 0.72
P-Value		0.781	0.001
Means carrying different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at ($P \leq 0.05$) or highly significantly different at $P < 0.01$. Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at ($P > 0.05$).			

The recorded values of ambient temperature revealed a non-significant differences ($P > 0.05$) neither during the period of LRF challenge to buffalo calves nor during sampling times. On the other hand; relative

humidity revealed a highly significant differences ($P < 0.01$) in both periods of time (challenge time and sampling days) as showed in table (1). Although, the little variation in ambient temperature and high

variation in relative humidity suggesting the extreme effect they have on ruminal activity and the variation of ruminal pH, microbial diversity, microbial count and motility as well as biochemical component of ruminal fluid in special attendance to treated group (challenged with LRF) and to some extent in control group. Examination of table (2&3) revealed that buffalo calves suffered from simple indigestion showed a highly significant reduction ($P < 0.01$) in ruminal pH, protozoal motility, Log Total Protozoal

Count (TPC), Log Total Anaerobic Bacterial Count (TBC), Log Lactobacillus count and Log Ruminococcus count, furthermore there were a highly significant reduction ($P < 0.01$) in the mean values of glucose and ammonia level in ruminal fluid in diseased group in compared with the control one, while there were a non-significant change ($P > 0.05$) in lactate level in ruminal fluid in both diseased and control group as shown in table (4).

Table 2. The mean values \pm S.E of ruminal fluid pH and protozoal motility of Egyptian buffalo calves treated with LRF in relation to time factor.

Group		Parameter	Ruminal pH	Protozoal motility
G _s	Group (1)		6.73 ^b \pm 0.12	\pm
	Group (2)		7.01 ^a \pm 0.10	+++
P- value			0.001	0.001
Group * Time				
G (1)	Zero time		6.43 ^c \pm 0.13	\pm
	1 st week		7.30 ^a \pm 0.06	+++
	2 nd week		6.40 ^c \pm 0.06	++
	3 rd week		6.8 ^{cd} \pm 0.06	+
G (2)	Zero time		6.9 ^{bc} \pm 0.13	++
	1 st week		7.30 ^a \pm 0.05	+++
	2 nd week		6.6 ^{de} \pm 0.09	++
	3 rd week		7.2 ^{ab} \pm 0.03	++
P- value			0.054	0.055

Means carrying different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at ($P \leq 0.05$) or highly significantly different at ($P < 0.01$).
 Means carrying the same superscripts in the column row are non-significantly different at ($P > 0.05$).

The pH of ruminal fluid and protozoal motility of animals treated with LRF (Group1); showed a significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) within the 1st week after treatment that were nearly the same as in control group (Table 2). As time proceed the noticed improvement in pH in ruminal pH and protozoal motility was retracted with a significant decline ($P \leq 0.05$) by the end of 2nd week when compared to control group and this may be attributed to a highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) increase in log lactobacillus count during the same period of time (Table 3), and this is synchronized with a significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) in

lactate level of ruminal fluid (Table 4). A second wave of a significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) in ruminal pH was detected by the end of the 3rd week of treatment. A week positive correlations (+0.69); (0.99); (0.87) was noticed between ruminal pH; protozoal motility, and log TPC with log TBC respectively. The ambient temperature and relative humidity showed strong positive correlations (+0.29); (+0.11) to ruminal pH, while protozoal motility revealed strong negative correlations (-0.24); (-0.32) to temperature and relative humidity, respectively.

Table 3. The mean values ± S.E of ruminal Log protozoal and bacterial count (TBC, Lactobacillus & Ruminococcus count) of Egyptian buffalo calves treated with LRF in relation to time factor.

Log count		Log			
Items	Log TPC /ml	Log TBC /ml	Lactobacillus count /ml	Ruminococcus count /ml	
G ₂	Group (1)	5.1985 ^b ±0.33	6.7696 ^b ±0.468	5.7443 ^b ±0.28	5.5172 ^b ±0.11
	Group (2)	6.0677 ^a ±0.10	6.9497 ^a ±0.219	5.8155 ^a ±0.39	6.1453 ^a ±0.10
P- value		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Group * Time					
G ₁	Zero time	4.7226 ^e ±0.06	6.7263 ^c ±0.04	5.0788 ^f ±0.04	5.2796 ^f ±0.05
	1 st week	6.0829 ^b ±0.01	7.9807 ^a ±0.01	5.5520 ^d ±0.01	5.4148 ^e ±0.01
	2 nd week	4.7581 ^e ±0.01	5.8238 ^e ±0.01	6.2784 ^b ±0.02	5.6842 ^d ±0.003
	3 rd week	5.2303 ^d ±0.02	6.5475 ^d ±0.02	6.0682 ^c ±0.01	5.6901 ^d ±0.01
G ₂	Zero time	6.2437 ^a ±0.01	6.7757 ^c ±0.002	5.2206 ^e ±0.02	6.4034 ^a ±0.01
	1 st week	6.2170 ^a ±0.03	7.5681 ^b ±0.007	6.4760 ^a ±0.02	6.1454 ^b ±0.02
	2 nd week	5.8843 ^c ±0.02	6.6857 ^c ±0.06	6.4666 ^a ±0.02	6.0170 ^c ±0.004
	3 rd week	5.9257 ^c ±0.02	6.7694 ^c ±0.05	5.0989 ^f ±0.04	6.0156 ^c ±0.003
P- value		0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

Means carrying different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at (P ≤ 0.05) or highly significantly different at (P < 0.01). Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at (P > 0.05).

Log TPC and Log TBC from ruminal fluid of animals challenged with LRF revealed a highly significant increase (P < 0.01) after one week of treatment. The improvement of log TPC was attributed to the synchronized increase in log TBC, as ruminal protozoa considered to be predator to ruminal bacteria as they digest the engulfed bacteria and utilize the resultant products to satisfy their needs for preformed amino acids; **Belzecki, et al., (2013)**. This improvement in both parameters was lost with a high significant decline (P < 0.01) by the end of the 2nd week of treatment when compared to log counts from control animals; and this may be attributed to the highly significant increase of log lactobacillus count, which in-turn caused a reduction of ruminal pH that was determinant to both anaerobic ruminal protozoa and bacteria. A second highly significant increase (P < 0.01) in Log TPC & Log TBC was noticed by the end of 3rd week of treatment; as shown in (Table 3). A week positive correlation (+0.88) between log TPC and log TBC, and a strong negative correlation (-0.07); (-0.53) between log lactobacillus and log TPC; log TBC was observed respectively. On another view, log

TPC revealed strong positive correlation (+0.28), and very strong positive correlation (+0.03) to temperature and relative humidity respectively. On the other hand Log TBC showed weak positive (+0.67), and strong negative (-0.23) to temperature and relative humidity respectively. Log Lactobacillus count from ruminal fluid of animals challenged with LRF revealed a highly significant increase (P < 0.01) as time proceed until the end of the 2nd week. A highly significant decline (P < 0.01) in Log Lactobacillus count was noticed in animals challenged with LRF by the end of 3rd week of treatment (Table 3). Log Lactobacillus count showed a strong negative correlation (-0.06) with ruminal pH and a strong positive correlation (+0.48) with lactate level in ruminal fluid. Weak negative correlation (-0.9) was observed between log Lactobacillus count and temperature, and positive correlation (+0.55) with relative humidity. Log Ruminococcus count from ruminal fluid of LRF challenged group announced a highly significant gradual increase (P < 0.01) as time proceed until the end of the 2nd week, then animals maintained this highly significant increase

($P < 0.01$) without further improvement until the end of the 3rd week of challenge, (Table 3). Log Ruminococcus count showed a strong positive correlation (+0.48) with

glucose level in ruminal fluid, weak negative (-0.84) and weak positive (+0.69) correlation to temperature and relative humidity, respectively.

Table 4. The mean values \pm S.E of ruminal fluid biochemical analysis of Egyptian buffalo calves treated with LRF in relation to time factor.

Treatment	Analytes	Glucose (mg/dL)	Lactate (mg/dL)	Ammonia (μ mol/L)	SCFA's (mEq/dL)
G _s	Group (1)	4.23 ^b \pm 0.68	1.45 ^a \pm 0.25	1236.5 ^b \pm 117.4	6.2 ^a \pm 1.79
	Group (2)	8.73 ^a \pm 0.16	1.35 ^a \pm 0.18	1444.2 ^a \pm 15.9	6.1 ^a \pm .73
P- value		0.001	0.601	0.001	0.190
Group * Time					
G (1)	Zero time	2.13 ^d \pm 0.28	0.51 ^d \pm 0.06	590.4 ^f \pm 6.93	4.8 ^c \pm 0.05
	1 st week	4.56 ^c \pm 0.15	2.19 ^{ab} \pm 0.10	1273.3 ^e \pm 6.31	7.2 ^a \pm 0.07
	2 nd week	2.43 ^d \pm 0.12	2.32 ^a \pm 0.08	1512.5 ^c \pm 6.07	6.3 ^b \pm 0.05
	3 rd week	7.80 ^b \pm 0.06	0.79 ^{cd} \pm 0.03	1569.9 ^a \pm 4.37	6.5 ^b \pm 0.03
G (2)	Zero time	8.80 ^a \pm 0.30	1.41 ^{abcd} \pm 0.37	1420.5 ^d \pm 2.89	4.8 ^c \pm 0.18
	1 st week	8.36 ^{ab} \pm 0.09	1.35 ^{bcd} \pm 0.41	1417.93 ^d \pm 6.96	6.4 ^b \pm 0.08
	2 nd week	8.80 ^a \pm 0.57	1.59 ^{abc} \pm 0.56	1404.6 ^d \pm 9.17	6.7 ^{ab} \pm 0.19
	3 rd week	8.96 ^a \pm 0.17	1.04 ^{cd} \pm 0.07	1533.63 ^b \pm 5.93	6.3 ^b \pm 0.32
P- value		0.001	0.022	0.001	0.053
Means carrying different superscripts in the same column are significantly different at ($P \leq 0.05$) or highly significantly different at $P < 0.01$).					
Means carrying the same superscripts in the same column are non-significantly different at ($P > 0.05$).					

Table (4), revealed a highly significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in the examined level of glucose from ruminal fluid of LRF challenged buffalo calves at the end of 1st week, followed by a highly significant decrease ($P < 0.01$) by the end of the 2nd week. A second wave of a highly significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in the ruminal fluid glucose was detected by the end of the 3rd week of challenge. Very strong positive correlation (+0.04), and weak positive one (+0.90) was calculated between glucose levels and temperature; RH, respectively.

Lactate levels of ruminal fluid among the challenged buffalo calves revealed a gradual significant increase ($P < 0.05$) synchronized with a gradual highly significant increase in log lactobacillus count ($P < 0.01$) during the 1st and 2nd weeks of challenge, followed by a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) and a highly significant decrease ($P < 0.01$) in lactate levels of ruminal fluid and log lactobacillus count consequently by the end of the 3rd

week of challenge; (Table 3, 4). Lactate levels showed weak negative correlation (-0.61) to ambient temperature, and strong negative correlation (-0.32) to relative humidity.

Examination of table (4) revealed a highly significant increase ($P < 0.01$) of ammonia levels of challenged calves' ruminal fluid as time proceed to the end of the 3rd week of challenge, and this may be attributed to excessive degradation of feed protein and lysis and breakdown of microbial protein (recycling) within the rumen; **Sanjay Kumar R Karnati, (2006)**. Ammonia levels of ruminal fluid showed strong negative correlation (-0.21) with log TBC and strong positive correlation (+0.26) with log TPC. On the other hand, weak negative (-0.74) and weak positive (+0.63) correlation was detected between ammonia levels and ambient temperature; relative humidity, respectively.

Meanwhile, SCFA's concentration in ruminal fluid among the challenged buffalo calves revealed a significant increase ($P < 0.05$) by the end of 1st week, followed by a significant decline ($P < 0.05$) starting from the 2nd week and this declaim was maintained until the end of 3rd week of treatment. Strong positive correlation (+0.493);(+0.492); (+0.387) was detected between concentration of SCFA's and ruminal glucose level, log Ruminococcus count and log TBC respectively, while there

was a week positive correlation (+0.774) with log TPC.

4. Conclusion & Recommendation

Lyophilized rumen fluid (LRF) challenge in the calves diagnosed with simple indigestion; was able to temporary enhance their health status based on the measured parameters, but this enhancement was rapidly retracted for reasons as insufficient dose of challenge over time. Longer period of treatment is recommended with higher doses to maintain the measured enhancement in the present work.

Acknowledgment

Great thanks to Suez Canal University sector of environmental affairs for its financial support. Also, Sincere thanks to **Dr. Sherif A. Moawed** (Lecturer of Bio-Statistics, Department of Animal Wealth, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University, and Ismailia, Egypt)

5. References:

Abo-Donia FM, Ghada S Ibrahim, Safaa Nadi, MS Sayah (2011). Effect of Inoculating New Born Lambs with Fresh or Lyophilized Rumen Fluid on Rumen Activity and Lamb Performance. *Journal of American Science*, 2011; 7 (9), 409 – 422.

Adrian L Cookson, Samantha J Noel, William J Kelly, Graeme T Attwood (2004). The use of PCR for the identification and characterization of bacteriocin genes from bacterial strains isolated from rumen or caecal contents of cattle and sheep. *FEMS (Federation of European Microbiological Societies) Microbiology Ecology* 48, 199–207.

Alonson AN (1979). Diagnostic analysis of rumen fluid. *Veterinary clinics of North America: Large animal practice*, Vol .1, No. (2): 363 - 376.

Anwar A Abdulla (2014). Antimicrobial Activity of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* that carry the Bacteriocin Gene. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Science* Volume 3 Number 6 (2014) pp. 269-276. **APHA (2001).** American Pharmaceutical Association 148th Annual Meeting. March 16- 20, 2001; San Francisco, California.

Belzecki, R Miltko, E Kwiatkowska, T Michalowski (2013): The ability of rumen ciliates, *Eudiplodinium maggii*,

Diploplastron affine, and *Entodinium caudatum*, to use the murein saccharides. *Folia Microbiol.* Vol. 58:463-468. 2013.

Bhatta R, Tajima K, Kurihara M (2006). Influence of temperature and pH on fermentation pattern and methane production in the rumen simulating fermenter (RUSITEC). *Asian-Aust Journal of Animal Science*; 19:376–80. 2006.

Bramley E, Lean J, Fulkerson WJ, Stevenson MA, Rabiee AR and Costa ND (2008). The Definition of Acidosis in Dairy Herds Predominantly Fed on Pasture and Concentrates. *Journal of Dairy Science.* Vol. 91:308–321.

Chandrasekharaiah M, Thulasi A, Sampath KT (2004). Selection of transformants of *Escherichia coli* containing cellulase gene from *Ruminococcus albus* isolated from rumen of crossbred steers. *Indian Journal of Biotechnology*, Vol 3, pp 431-434. 2004.

Cruickshank R, Duguid JP, Marimion BP, Swain RH (1975). *Medical Microbiology, the Practice of Medical Microbiology.* 12th Ed, Vol. 11, Churchill Livingstone Limited, Edinburgh, London and New York.

Cruickshank R, Duguid JP, Marimion BP, Swain RH (1980). *Medical Microbiology*". E.L.B.S., 12th Ed, Vol. 11,

Reprinted Churchill Livingstone and Robert Stevenson, Edinburgh, EHI, 3AF.

Deng W, Dongmei X, Huaming M, Metha W (2008). The use of molecular techniques based on ribosomal RNA and DNA for rumen microbial ecosystem studies: a review. *Mol. Biol. Rep.* Vol. 35:265–274.

DN Kamra (2005). Rumen microbial ecosystem. *Current Science*, Vol. 89, NO. 1, 10 July 2005.

Duncan (1955). Multiple range and multiple F tests. *Biometrics* 11:1 - 42, 1955.

Fouda TA (1995). Clinical and biochemical studies on the primary ruminal dysfunction in sheep. Ph. D. Thesis (Veterinary Medicine), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Suez Canal University.

Fulekar (Ed.), MH (2009). Bioinformatics: Applications in Life and Environmental Sciences, Springer (pp. 110)

Hajikolaei MR, Nouri M, Saberi Afshar F, Jafari DA (2006). Effect of experimentally induced ruminal lactic acidosis on blood pH, Bicarbonate and Pco₂ in the Sheep. *Pakistan journal of biological science*. Vol. 9, No. (10):2003-2005.

Herigstad B, Hamilton M, Heersink J (2001). How to optimize the drop plate method for enumerating bacteria. *J. Microbiol. Meth.* 44(2):121-129.

Houda Bouraoui, Elena Vendramin, Andrea Squartini, Mohamed-Laid Haddi (2011). Taxonomical analysis of the suspended bacterial fraction in the dromedary rumen fluid. *African Journal of Biotechnology* Vol. 10 (76), pp. 17640-17644.

Jens Christian Pedersen (1992). Natamycin as a Fungicide in Agar Media. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, p. 1064-1066.

JS Shen, Z Chai, LJ Song, JX Liu, YM Wu (2012). Insertion depth of oral stomach tubes may affect the fermentation parameters of ruminal fluid collected in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science* Vol. 95 No. 10:5978–5984.

Konitzer K, Voigt S (1963). Clinical chemistry. *Acta*, 8, 5.

Levesque (2007). SPSS Programming and Data Management: A Guide for SPSS and

SAS Users, Fourth Edition (2007), SPSS Inc., Chicago Ill.

Lodge-Ivey SL, J Browne-Silva, MB Horvath (2009). Technical note: Bacterial diversity and fermentation end products in rumen fluid samples collected via oral lavage or rumen cannula. *J. Anim. Sci.* 87:2333–2337.

Mahdy RA, Nada WM, Wageh MM (2010). Topical amphotericin B and subconjunctival injection of fluconazole (combination therapy) versus topical amphotericin B (monotherapy) in treatment of keratomycosis. *J. Ocul Pharmacol Ther.*; 26(3):281-5.

Nagaraja TG, Titgemeyer EC (2007). Ruminal Acidosis in Beef Cattle: The Current Microbiological and Nutritional Outlook. *Journal of Dairy Science*. Vol. 90: 17–38. 2001.

Nikki Kenters, Gemma Henderson, Jeyamalar Jeyanathan, Sandra Kittelmann, Peter H Janssen (2011). Isolation of previously uncultured rumen bacteria by dilution to extinction using a new liquid culture medium. *Journal of Microbiological Methods* 84, 52-60.

Patrick R Murray, Michael A Pfaller, Ellen Jo Baron (1999). Manual of Clinical Microbiology 7th Edition. American Society for Microbiology Publishing, Washington, D.C. 20005.

Radostits OM, Gay CC, Hinchcliff KW, Constable PD (2007). *Veterinary Medicine*. 10th edition. A textbook of the diseases of cattle, horses, sheep, pigs and goats. London, Philadelphia, New York.

Ratib MH (2001). Correlation between some ruminal contents and the respective morphological changes in sheep in Assiut governorate. M.V.Sc. Fac.of Vet.Medicine, Assiut university.

RZ Zhong, HX Sun, GD Li, HW Liu, DW Zhou (2014). Effects of inoculation with rumen fluid on nutrient digestibility, growth performance and rumen fermentation of early weaned lambs. *Livestock Science* 162 (2014) 154–158.

Salah Abd-Elmohsen Galbt (2007). Studies on cryopreservation of ruminal fauna in sheep. Ph. D. Thesis (Veterinary

Medicine), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Benha University.

Sanjay Kumar R Karnati (2006): Application of molecular techniques to assess changes in ruminal microbial populations and protozoal generation time in cows and continuous culture. Dissertation, Ohio State University, 2006.

Snedecor George W, Cochran William G (1989). Statistical Methods, Eighth Edition, Iowa State University Press.

Stigler, Stephen M (1989). Francis Galton's Account of the Invention of Correlation. *Statistical Science* 4 (2): 73–79.

Tajima K, Nonaka I, Higuchi K, Takusari N, Kurihara M, Takenaka A, Aminov R (2007). Influence of high temperature and humidity on rumen bacterial diversity in Holstein heifers. *Anaerobe*, 13(2), 57-64 .2006.

Wang MZ, HR Wang, LH Yu (2009). Effect of NDF content on protozoal community and grazing rate in rumen. *J. Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 8: 1749-1752.

William J Ripple, Pete Smith, Helmut Haberl, Stephen A. Montzka, Clive McAlpine, Douglas H Boucher (2014). Ruminants, climate change and climate policy. *Nature Climate Change*, vol. 4, January 2014.

Young DS (2001). Effect of disease on clinical laboratory test, 4th edition. AACC.

Zelver N, Hamilton M, Pitts B, Goeres D, Walker D, Sturman P, Heersink J (1999). Measuring antimicrobial effects on biofilm bacteria: in R. J. Doyle, et al. (eds), *biofilm: methods in enzymology*, Academic Press, San Diego, CA, pp. 608-628.